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PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED IN IMPLEMENTING MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the problems encountered in implementing modular distance learning in selected public elementary schools in Bongabong North District. Specifically, it sought to determine the profile of teachers in terms of teaching experience, civil status, academic rank, and highest educational attainment; the extent of the problems encountered in implementation concerning preparation, distribution, retrieval, and checking of pupil's answers; and the relationship between them. This study used descriptive-correlational research methods and researcher-made instruments that underwent validation and reliability testing. Results showed that teachers were cautious when considering student responses. With this, teachers only have problems in checking pupils' answers.

Keywords: Modular Distance Learning, Problems encountered, Public Elementary School Teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd) developed a distance learning mode for pupils a year ago. It is a learning delivery modality designed in which teachers and pupils do not interact physically. Independent learners and pupils with the assistance of parents, relatives, or family members are most suited to distance learning (Sadiq & Zamir, 2015). Based on DepEd's survey, most schools used this learning modality nationwide, and learning through printed and digital modules was the most preferred by parents with children enrolled this academic year. (Bernardo, 2020)

Pupils participating in modular distance learning can complement their studies with self-learning modules (SLM) that are either printed or available in digital format. Meanwhile, teachers used e-mail, text messages, instant messaging (chat), or the telephone to monitor and guide pupils' development. These self-studying modules contain pre-tests, discussions, and a sequence of assessments. Teachers distributed these to all learners with the attached schedule. They play a crucial role in providing excellent education during the pandemic. Individualized pedagogy was provided using modular distance learning, allowing pupils to employ self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, depending on their requirements. Other resources, such as learner's materials, textbooks, activity sheets,

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study guides, and other study materials, are available to modular distance learning pupils (Llego, 2021).

However, teachers need help figuring out how to use their newly created and established curriculum-based innovations in classrooms where face-to-face, direct physical instruction between teachers and pupils is still needed. When schools are still open for face-to-face learning, using and benefiting fully from the developed technologies is a significant and severe problem. According to Canonizado (2021), teachers have run into problems such as reaching out to all of the pupils at home even though they are using various ways of communication. Also, the errors bothered teachers, who were concerned that some pupils might not have guardians present when the lessons were studied and that no one would be available to correct them. Teachers' role is typically limited to module development, distribution, and retrieval, as well as answering inquiries from parents and correcting learners' responses. These problems impact their ability to prepare, distribute, retrieve, and evaluate pupils' answers.

The shift from teaching-learning in schools to modular distance studying made it extra challenging for school personnel to change exceptional primary schooling. That is why DepEd administrators always find avenues to solve crises and capacitate their teachers and school heads to become more remarkably effective in modular distance learning (Bagood, 2020). He added that identified teaching personnel and the Education Program Supervisors organized modules beginning in May 2020 in all topics for all grades/year degrees throughout four quarters according to the Essential Learning Competencies.

As a result of this research, the study's primary idea focused on the teachers' reactions to the Department of Education's new learning modalities (DepEd). It also assessed and provided a clear lens on teachers' experiences, difficulties, and challenges in this new regular education. Make recommendations for short course offerings intended for adult learners, particularly teachers in private and public schools, to prepare them for this new era of dealing with technology in the delivery of instruction. This research aims to learn about the resources, preparedness, and communication problems teachers at selected schools in Bongabong North District have when implementing modular distance learning.

This research also attempted to determine the approaches, interventions, or solutions educational institutions and the government use to assist pupils, parents, and teachers struggling with this new learning mode. This study's findings may serve as a springboard for future research, improvements to existing school programs, and instructions for implementing modular distance learning.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed the descriptive design. It is used to measure the extent of problems teachers encounter in terms of preparation, distribution, retrieval of modules, and checking of pupils' answers, as well as the profile of teachers in terms of length of service, civil status, academic rank, and educational attainment.

The study used a researcher-made instrument that is composed of two parts. Part I assessed the teacher's profile concerning the length of teaching experience, civil status, academic rank, and highest educational attainment. At the same time, the second determined the extent of problems encountered by the teachers in terms of preparation, distribution, retrieval of modules, and checking pupils' answers. Upon validation, using Pearson's *r*, the reliability of the self-made questionnaires was determined. The computed

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reliability was 0.8728, preparation of modules; 0.8333, distribution of modules; 0.8982, retrieval of modules; and 0.8303, checking of pupil's answer.

In data gathering, the researchers sent a request letter to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Oriental Mindoro for approval. Upon approval for coordination and consent, the proponent presented it to the school-respondent principal. The statistical tools used were Descriptive and Inferential Statistics: Weighted Mean, frequency, and percentage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of Teachers

Length of Teaching Experience.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Teachers in terms of length of teaching experience

Length of Teaching Experience	Freque ⁿ c	
	y	Percentage
1-5 years	4	6
6-10 years	15	23
11-15 years	10	16
16-20 years	9	14
21-25 years	8	13
26-30 years	11	17
31-35 years	5	8
36-40 years	2	3
Total	64	100

Table 1 presents the length of service, 15 or 20% had spent 6-10 years in teaching, 11 or 17% spent 26-30 years in teaching, 10 or 16% spent 11-15 years in teaching, 9 or 14% of teachers served for 16-20 years in teaching, 8 or 13% had teaching experience for 21-25 years, 5 or 8% served for 31-35 years in teaching, 4 or 6% give their time and efforts for 1-5 years and lastly, 2 or 3% of teachers had teaching experience for 36-40 years.

Civil Status.

Table 2. Demographic Profile of Teachers in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Freque ⁿ c	
	y	Percentage
Single	3	5
Married	59	92
Widow	2	3
Total	64	100

Table 2 shows the civil status; 59 or 92% of teacher respondents were married, 3 or 5% reported that they were single at the time of the survey, and 2 or 3% of the teacher respondents reported that they were widowed.

Academic Rank.

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Table 3. Demographic Profile of Teachers in terms of Academic Rank

Academic Rank	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	9	14
Teacher II	17	27
Teacher III	38	59
Total	64	100

Table 3 reveals the academic rank; 59% were teacher III; on the other hand, 17 or 27% of teachers were teacher II, and 9 or 14% of respondents were teacher I.

Highest Educational Attainment.

Table 4 shows the highest educational attainment of the teacher-respondents; 23, or 36%, graduated with a Master's Degree, and 21, or 33%, reported a Bachelor of Elementary Education as their highest educational attainment. 17 or 27% of respondents have the Complete Academic Requirement for a Master's Degree (CARMA), 2 or 3% of teacher respondents are Doctors Degree Holders. Lastly, 1 or 2% of teacher respondents had AB w/ Education Units as their highest educational attainment.

Table 4. Demographic Profile of Teachers in terms Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
BEED	21	33
MAED Graduate	23	36
Doctoral Degree	2	3
MAED CARMA	17	27
AB w/ Educ. Units	1	2
Total	64	100

Problems Encountered by Teachers in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning

Preparation of Modules.

Table 5. Extent of Problems Encountered by Teachers in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in terms of Preparation of Modules

Item	WM	Rank	Description
I need more time and assistance in preparing modules.	2.48	5	Low Extent
I need more materials and supplies when preparing and printing the	2.36	6	Low Extent
I need help preparing the modules, especially when the printer is not	3.14	1	High Extent
I need help printing a mass production of modules.	2.86	2	High Extent

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Power interruption delays the module reproduction.	2.62	3	High Extent
I overworked myself and spent sleepless hours printing all the modules, resulting in exhaustion.	2.61	4	High Extent
In preparing modules, I observed a lack of activities and assessments that occurred.	2.16	9	Low Extent
Some of the lessons are inappropriate for the pupils.	2.22	8	Low Extent
When printing, the modules show smudges, faded type, and poor image quality.	2.25	7	Low Extent
I need to learn how to use modern technology well enough.	1.58	10	Very Low Extent
Overall Mean	2.43		Low Extent

Table 5 shows preparation of modules. Results show that the problems encountered by teachers in modular distance learning in terms of module preparation, as shown on the overall mean of 2.43, are described as low extent.

Results imply that the teacher respondents revealed that the problems they encountered regarding the preparation of modules were related to the materials and supplies. It means that when the printer is not working, the teachers have a hard time preparing and printing the modules, which results in late distribution and mass production of modules. On the other hand, the teacher needs to learn how to use modern technology well enough, and teachers need help with disruptions that the technologies can bring and have their work negatively impacted or have not used technologies effectively, which adds more time to prepare the modules.

Distribution of Modules.

Table 6. Extent of Problems Encountered by Teachers in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in terms of Distribution of Modules

Items	WM	Rank	Description
I need help distributing due to a need for printed modules.	1.89	8	Low Extent
It takes work to give directions to parents.	2.38	3	Low Extent
Some parents claim the modules after two weeks or more.	2.89	1	High Extent
Some parents are complaining about the number of modules.	2.52	2	High Extent
Attendance takes longer because some parents need to bring their ballpens.	2.08	5	Low Extent
I experience difficulties in distributing modules due to student's location.	1.95	7	Low Extent
In the distribution of modules, some parents are impatient and demanding.	2.02	6	Low Extent
Pupils and parents picked up the wrong modules, which added to the time spent locating and contacting the parents.	1.64	10	Very Low Extent
I needed help contacting parents and students to get their	1.86	9	Low Extent

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modules because most gave me the wrong phone number.			
I experience difficulties because of parents' poor cooperation.	2.19	4	Low Extent
Overall Mean	2.14		Low Extent

Table 6 presents the distribution of modules. The result shows that the problems teachers encounter regarding the distribution of modules, as shown on the overall mean of 2.14, are described as low extent.

Results imply that the teacher's problems in the distribution of modules relate to the late claiming of modules because of parents' hectic work schedules. It means pupils will have less time to answer their modules, resulting in late retrieval.

Retrieval of Modules.

Table 7. Extent of Problems Encountered by Teachers in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in terms of Retrieval of Modules

Item	WM	Rank	Description
Some parents need to follow the submission date of pupil's modules.	2.84	2	High Extent
Due to health issues, I had to postpone the retrieval of modules.	2.08	9	Low Extent
Modules are submitted incomplete and crumpled.	2.53	4	High Extent
Some pupils need to submit their modules.	2.36	5	Low Extent
Refusal of modules takes two or more weeks due to the student's location.	2.33	7	Low Extent
In retrieving modules, some parents need to follow the health protocols.	2.22	8	Low Extent
Some pupils were the ones who retrieved their modules because their parents were busy.	2.44	6	Low Extent
Modules are sometimes mistakenly disposed of, and as a result, they still need to be returned.	1.92	10	Low Extent
Some parents should have guided their children in answering modules, which delays module retrieval.	2.95	1	High Extent
Parent's late retrieval produces a backlog of pupil's modules.	2.70	3	High Extent
Overall Mean	2.44		Low Extent

Table 7 reveals the retrieval of modules. The result shows the problems encountered by teachers in terms of retrieval of modules, as shown in the overall mean of 2.4, which is a low extent.

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Results imply that the teacher's problem in retrieving modules is associated with the parent's responsibility in guiding their children in answering modules that can cause the pupil's failure to submit modules with complete answers. Modular learning is complex, and pupils must read and reread. This only appeals to a few pupils today, so they will almost certainly ask their parents or guardians to answer their modules. Pupils understand that it is their responsibility to work on their modules. However, if parents and other guardians do not uphold this value, the pupils will quickly disregard the rule, which could become a habit. On the other hand, modules are sometimes mistakenly disposed of, so they must still be returned.

Checking of Pupil's Answer.

Table 8. Extent of Problems Encountered by Teachers in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in terms of Checking of Pupil's Answers

Item	WM	Rank	Description
Some pupil's activities have yet to answer.	2.95	2	High Extent
Some pupil's modules have no name.	2.56	4	High Extent
I encountered many things that could have been improved in pupils' answer sheets.	2.59	3	High Extent
Some parents seemed complicated to contact when we had concerns about pupil's modules.	2.33	9	Low Extent
Some modules have irrelevant answers or are not related to the questions.	2.36	8	Low Extent
I needed help understanding students' modules due to their faded answers.	2.09	10	Low Extent
I needed help in validating my pupil's output.	2.48	5.5	Low Extent
I need help in checking the modules of pupils due to limited time.	2.48	5.5	Low Extent
I need help contacting my pupils' parents to monitor their progress and answer their queries.	2.41	7	Low Extent
I encountered modules answered by their parents.	3.30	1	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	2.56		High Extent

Table 8 shows the check pupils' answers. The result shows teachers' problems regarding checking modules, as shown in the overall mean of 2.55, a high extent. It means the pupils are interested in something other than the learning process. Many parents agree to answer their children's modules because they cannot wait for them to work. Some pupils may need to submit their modules on time, so parents take the initiative to answer them for their children. Alternatively, they do the work simply because they want their children to do well.

Nevertheless, this practice only helps the pupils and ignores the virtue of Honesty. The practice of relying on parents and laziness is encouraged and addresses the lack of motivation. On the other hand, teachers needed help understanding pupils' modules due to their faded answers. Teachers may notice faded answers but still record the submitted answers. Results imply that the teacher's problem in checking pupils' answers is when they recognize that the parents are the ones who answer their children's modules..

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CONCLUSIONS

The following are the conclusions drawn based on the findings of the study:

1. The profile reveals various characteristics related to their teaching experience, civil status, academic rank, and highest educational attainment. Regarding teaching experience, a significant percentage of teachers have spent between 6-10 years and 26-30 years teaching. Most are married, and Teacher III is the most common academic rank. Furthermore, the highest educational attainment varies, with many holding a Master's Degree.
2. The study identified several issues regarding the implementation of modular distance learning: difficulty when the printer is not working; utilization of modern technology effectively, especially for students who need access to such resources; claiming of modules after an extended period, causing delays in the learning process; delays when parents failed to guide their children in answering the modules; mistaken disposal of modules also caused setbacks in retrieving them; parents answering their children's modules, indicating a need for more student engagement in the learning process; faded answers in the modules made it difficult for teachers to accurately understand and assess student responses.

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